

IMPACT OF SOCIAL SKILLS TRAINING ON SHYNESS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN YORRO LGA, TARABA STATE

Emmanuel Tersoo Danjuma and Aisha Nafisat Abdullahi

Department of Guidance and Counselling, Taraba State University, Jalingo, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17303564>

Abstract

This study examined the effect of social skills training on Secondary School Students' Shyness in the Yorro Local Government Area in Taraba State, Nigeria. Two (2) Objectives were set to guide this study, and Two (2) null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 significance level. The study employed one group pre-test and post-test experimental design. The population comprised forty-three (43) students who exhibited symptoms of shyness in the selected secondary school in Yorro LGA in Taraba State, Nigeria. A sample of twenty (20) SS II students was selected through purposive sampling. The Shyness Personality Scale (SPS) consisting of 40 items with a test-retest reliability value of $r = 0.958$ was used for data collection. Mean, Standard Deviation and Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test were used to analyze the data. Findings reveal that students exposed to social skills training (SST) had reduced shy behaviour. The reduction in mean shyness scores from the pre-test to the post-test for both genders suggests that the intervention effectively decreased shyness levels. The slightly larger reduction in shyness scores for females compared to males indicates that the intervention may have been marginally more effective for females. The researchers therefore, concluded that social skills training effectively decreased secondary school students' shyness in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State. The findings of the study led to the recommendation that students should be encouraged to go to school counsellors for training on the use of social skills' training especially to curb behavioural problems such as shyness. (ii) Principals in federal schools, State schools and Proprietors of private schools should be encouraged to provide adequate counselling services phenomenon in schools and to employ the services of professional counsellors who will use Social Skills Training for effective treatment of students' behavioural problems such as shyness. (iii) Educational experts in counselling should be encouraged to use social skills training for effective treatment of shyness among secondary school students.

Keywords: Social Skills' Training, Secondary School Students, Shyness, Gender.

Introduction

Shyness is a behaviour mannerism characterized by social apprehension, dread, and selfconsciousness. Shyness is the discomfort that a shy person feels as a result of social developments, as evidenced by the shy person's feelings, self-evaluations, and behavioural patterns. D'Arcy (2016) noted that shyness is an emotion that shows how an individual feels and behaves in the presence of other people. Shyness is a defective behaviour that manifests itself in social circumstances in either an overt or hidden manner in children, adolescents, and adults. A shy person avoids, withdraws, evades social situations. Uba and Idieune (2016) stated that shy students are prone to not participating in class activities like answering or asking questions and decline to take part in many social and academic opportunities. Anxiety may overtake this group of students, making it difficult for them to focus on academic pursuits. Ibaishwa (2014) believes that shy students are often not able to function effectively with their peers and others.

More so, Uba and Idieune (2016) asserted that shyness is a severe case of social anxiety. Oguzie, Ezunu, Uba and Osagie-Obazee (2018) opined shyness to be a form of excessive selffocus, an obsession with a person's thoughts and feelings which always leads the person to an unwanted behaviour or action. Shyness is a personal experience that is exhibited through apprehension and nervousness in social encounters. Furthermore, Oguzie, Obi and Nnadi (2019) opined that shy behaviour is a serious problem among students in secondary schools in Imo state, and Nigeria at large. McAdams (2014) reported that students who have shy behaviour might not get the benefits from communication-oriented classroom learning activities like group discussions, seminars or debates, which likewise, are liable to cause generalized social obsession or avoidant personality malady. To say the least, shyness could lead to social phobia, avoidance of communication and low self-esteem because of lack of confidence in public speaking. People need people for survival, for the quest for satisfaction and socialization. Given that social interaction and relationships are important for the quality of life and positive mental health (Datta, Datta, & Majumdar, 2015).

During school, some students engage in numerous maladaptive behaviours that may jeopardize the peaceful coexistence and productive interpersonal relationships that are expected to characterize every school as a social environment. As a result, some of the pupils' maladaptive behaviours are readily apparent, while others are not. Those who are easily recognized are usually given more attention and rectified, whilst those who are not easily noticed are frequently ignored or completely ignored. Being shy is one of these maladaptive behaviours of students who do not receive the attention they deserve for correction. Royal, Hedgpeth and Flammer (2018) asserted that shyness is "the tendency to feel awkward, worried, or tense during social encounters, especially with unfamiliar people" and discussed its negative impact on students' mental and social wellness, highlighting how shyness can lead to feelings of unease and insecurity. Shy people may experience bodily symptoms such as blushing or feeling silent, jittery, or out of breath. Shy people may also acquire bad feelings about themselves and excessive worry about how others perceive them, as well as unusual sweating, heartbeat, and stomach distress. Shyness can harm people's thinking, feelings, mood, memory, and capacity to operate in social circumstances. Shyness is a major issue among students in secondary school. The importance of assisting students in overcoming shyness cannot be overstated.

Hall and Merolla (2020) opined that Humans are social, gregarious beings who need to relate with each other to meet their biological, emotional and social needs. Without the ability to communicate their needs and interests to others, their lives will be lonely and colourless, devoid of the warmth, meaning and nurturance that social contacts and relationships bring. Shyness affects people's social skills, mood, and sociability. Judging from its adverse consequences, shyness can lead to a reduction in the level of happiness, low self-esteem, and loneliness, along with social and emotional maladjustment. Supporting the above view, Rahmani and Baniyasi (2013) emphasized that shy people avoid relationships with others, deny responsibility to build relationships with others, and their anxiety becomes apparent when exposed to social exchanges and interactions. These assertions by implication suggest that shy behaviour can deter students' academic activities and in turn cause devastating effects on the students' social development in the future.

Efforts by parents, teachers, religious leaders, and counsellors appeared to have helped in some way to alleviate the dilemma of shy students, the effectiveness of such efforts remains debatable given the high rates of shy students in secondary schools. Since counsellors are responsible for helping students develop

and maintain positive behaviours, it is essential to look into more long-term and efficient counselling methods to address the issue of shyness among students. Therefore, the researchers selected a well-known behavioural treatment named social skills training to determine its effectiveness in lowering students' shyness in secondary school. The modification of thought process is the goal of this treatment technique and as such the researchers believe that this technique if applied in secondary schools in Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State will help to reduce students' shyness.

Training in social skills is a therapeutic approach, a form of behaviour therapy utilized by therapists, teachers, and trainers to help individuals who have difficulties relating to other people. The training consists of interventions and teaching strategies that assist people in understanding and enhancing their social behaviour. According to Côté, Larose, Geoffroy, Laurin, Vitaro, Tremblay & Morin (2017), training in social skills is a psychological intervention focusing on developing or improving social interactions, social appearance, or interpersonal skills. Social skills training is a technique used in training individuals and teaching them how to express their feelings and develop their social skills. This can assist them to achieve their goals and learn to live independently. Students' social skills, which are collections of learned behaviour that enable students to communicate with others, have been taken into account as one of the aspects of education.

The degree of an individual's social skills proficiency is directly linked to his or her social growth development and the quantity and quality of desirable social behaviours that he or she displays (Matson & Olandik cited in Kheirkhah, 2020). Considering social intelligence, social growth, and social education along with the other growth and educational dimensions has a particular significance since social skills remain the most crucial aspect of socialization. Vidyanand, Shriharsha and Natekar (2022) stated that training in social skills is one of the most effective managements for clients with self-esteem and social anxiety. Social skills training aims to assist people in comprehending the spoken and non-spoken behaviours that are a part of social relations. The improvement of social skills in interpersonal relationships requires emotional and psychological health and emotional intelligence. In this way, social skills are referred to the learnt and community-accepted behaviour. Improvement in social skills can assist students with behavioural disorders who struggle to express their feelings, emotions, and thoughts appropriately.

Training in social skills usually starts with the evaluation of the exact skill deficits. Trainers and Therapists could inquire about their clients' most difficult social circumstances or areas for skill improvement. Finding out which target groups are best suited for social skills training in the particular circumstance is the aim of this procedure. Once specific target areas have been selected, a set of approaches for enhancing social skills is offered. Usually, one area at a time is where changes are made to prevent feeling overwhelmed. Research on how social skills training affects certain personality traits has been conducted and the findings of these investigations revealed that social skills training increases self-esteem, social growth, personal adequacy, and adjustment as well as reduces inappropriate behaviours such as aggression and violence (Pasha & Gorjian cited in Ali, Abdel-Fatah, Mahmoud & El-Sayad, 2018). Social skills training programs encourage human interaction and are expected to improve the individual's skills of assertiveness and communication skills. It also allows the person to fulfil three objectives: a) Develop a good rapport with others,

- b) improve the ability to meet the demands of various social situations,
- c) Use appropriate communication techniques in social settings. (Guadalupe, 2016).

Anyone who wants to build relationships both personally and professionally should work on their social skills. Gaining social skills makes it easier to navigate social settings. Social skills training is typically provided to students who are deficient in social skills or who cannot interpret certain social clues. During therapy sessions, the participant practices certain behaviours to change his or her social behaviour patterns. The aim of social skills training is to enhance a person's capacity for social interaction in daily life. Social skills training aids in the mastery of particular abilities, such as enhancing the use of eye contact during conversation or reserving a specific amount of personal space from those who disrupt one's everyday routine. Techniques for teaching social skills include modelling, instruction, role-playing, reinforcing positive interactions, shaping, and feedback.

1. **Instruction:** Regarding instruction, social skills education and learning take place via the modelling of appropriate behaviours. For instance, instruction can be used to explain the distinctions between aggressive, passive, and assertive communication styles.
2. **Monitoring:** This is a method used to ask the person to keep looking someone in the eye while speaking.
3. **Positive/Corrective feedback:** This is a method for enhancing social skills and rewarding progress made during practice.
4. **Shaping:** This is a process whereby the individual that is being trained to acquire a new behaviour is reinforced each time he/she exhibits responses that are similar to the final goal, while those responses that are not similar to the final goal are not reinforced and as such they get eliminated (Ima-Osagie & Obineli, 2020).
5. **Behavioral Rehearsal/Role Play:** During role-play, patients practice newly acquired abilities in a simulated environment. Group members can provide comments to each other regarding their performance in simulated settings during role-playing exercises. For instance, participants could pretend to be consumer trying to return a faulty item to a store. The "customer's" responses might then be discussed by the other participants.
6. **Modelling technique** is a behavioural intervention in which an observer views a model engaged in an adaptive behaviour. It is an approach that involves the counsellor setting up an example for the client to follow, such as the ability to interact and socialize with friends and other people without feeling shy (Ima-Osagie & Nwankwo, 2019).
7. **Weekly homework assignments:** enable the newly acquired social skills to be practised outside of therapy.

Several people have not ever been taught the value of maintaining eye contact throughout a conversation or interpersonal skills like "small talk" in social situations. Furthermore, many are unable to discern the myriads of nonverbal clues that arise in social situations, like when somebody wants to shift the subject of discussion or change to another activity. Social skills training helps students understand how to read social cues so they can behave correctly in a variety of social settings. It is believed that through enhancing social abilities or altering particular behaviours, students can function effectively during social situations.

According to Igbokwe (2019), every nation, regardless of size, has accepted education as a legitimate platform for educating its people. Perhaps, this is basically because 'school' has been recognized as a hub for transformational learning and life skills. Oguzie, Ezunu, Uba and Osagie (2018) assert that the above statement highlights the rationale behind the school's widespread recognition as one of the main agencies

of socialization. During schooling, several students exhibit diverse forms of unwanted behaviour which could ruin the effective interpersonal relationships expected to be the distinguishing features of each school as a social setting. Thus, some of the unwanted behaviours displayed by students are quickly detected while some are not. The ones that are quickly detected are generally given attention, and the ones that are not quickly detected are most times neglected or given little attention. One such unwanted behaviour of secondary school students who are not given the desired attention is shyness. The problem of shyness among secondary school students has raised great concern in the Yorro LGA of Taraba State and the entire Nigerian society. Hence, this study examined the effect of social skills training on Secondary School Students' shyness in the Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State.

The researchers believed that the outcomes of this study would help to reduce the shy behaviour of students in secondary school in the Yorro LGA in Taraba State. This study would help students to understand the harmful effects of shy behaviour and exactly how school counsellors can assist them to adjust properly in social activities and acquire the ability to change from shy behaviour. Moreover, this study would inspire effective modification in the decrease of students' shyness in the secondary schools in Yorro LGA of Taraba State, and this will increase social relations among shy students and in turn, improve the student's academic performance. Furthermore, the current study will likely provide school counsellors and guidance officers with skills in behavioural treatment and as well the capacity to use the techniques on anyone with unwanted behaviour. Likewise, the report of this study would help in motivating the government to make funds available for the setting up of facilities for guidance and counselling, and the employment of trained personnel who will discharge the guidance and counselling services in the schools. The scope of this study is delimited to the effect of social skills training on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State. The independent variable is the effect of social skills training while the dependent variable is the students' shyness. The social skills training techniques used in this study include instruction (verbal communication and active listening), role-playing (making introductions, accepting and giving compliments, etc.) and reinforcing positive interactions. Only SS II students took part in the study. SS2 students were chosen for this study to solve their shy behavioural problems before graduating from secondary education. The present study would help reduce students' shy behaviour and improve their social life and educational attainments. The study was carried out in a public secondary school in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State. The research was conducted during the first term of the 2023/2024 academic session.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the efficacy of social skills training on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to determine the:

1. effectiveness of social skills training on secondary school students' anger in Yorro Local Government Area in Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. effectiveness of social skills training on male and female secondary school students' anger in Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. To what extent is the effect of social skills training on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State, Nigeria?

2. What is the difference in the mean shyness of high shyness male and female students exposed to social skills training in secondary schools in Yorro L.G.A. in Taraba State?

Statement of the Hypotheses

1. Social skills training does not have a significant effect on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State, Nigeria.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean shyness of male and female students exposed to social skills training in secondary schools in Yorro L. G. A. of Taraba State.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest research design, which was deemed appropriate given the school-based context of the research. As noted by Nworgu (2015), quasi-experimental designs are particularly suitable in educational settings where implementing a true experimental design may not be feasible due to potential disruptions to normal school routines. In a quasi-experimental framework, the researchers purposefully introduce an intervention and exercise control over participants' exposure to the treatment. In the present study, social skills training was introduced as the independent variable to reduce shyness among students. This deliberate intervention sought to bring about measurable changes in participants' behaviour, specifically targeting levels of shyness, which served as the dependent variable. A pretest was conducted to identify students exhibiting shyness, which guided the selection of the study sample and provided baseline data for subsequent comparison. Following the intervention, a post-test was administered to assess the impact of the social skills training and to determine the effectiveness of the treatment in modifying the target behaviour within the sample population.

The target population for this study comprised Senior Secondary School Two (SS II) students from a selected school in Yorro Local Government Area of Taraba State, Nigeria. A total of 43 students were initially identified as exhibiting symptoms of shyness based on their scores on the *Shyness Personality Scale* (SPS). Only students who scored between 100 and 200 on the SPS, indicating a high level of shyness, were considered eligible for inclusion in the study. From this group, a purposive sampling technique was employed to select a final sample of 20 students who met the criteria and voluntarily consented to participate in the intervention. Purposive sampling was chosen due to its suitability for selecting participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. This method allowed the researchers to ensure that all participants possessed the defining attributes of interest, in this case, high shyness levels, thereby enhancing the relevance and quality of the data collected. The selected sample consisted of 20 SS II students, comprising five (5) males and fifteen (15) females, who were treated as a single intervention group.

The instrument for data collection in this study was the Shyness Personality Scale (SPS), a standardized self-report measure comprising 40 items designed to assess varying levels of shyness among respondents. Each item is rated on a five-point rating scale: Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Not Sure (NS) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The total score ranges from 40 to 200, with higher scores indicating higher levels of shyness. For this study, scores between 100 and 200 were interpreted as representing high levels of shy behaviour. To establish the content validity of the instrument, the initial version of the SPS, along with the study objectives, was submitted to experts in the fields of Measurement and Evaluation, Guidance and Counselling, and Psychology at the Faculty of Education, Taraba State University. The experts in Guidance and Counselling Psychology were specifically tasked with evaluating

the scale due to the psychological and counselling nature of the constructs under investigation - shyness and social skills. The experts reviewed the items for relevance, clarity, and alignment with the study's objectives. Based on their feedback, several items were revised for improved clarity and appropriateness. For example, the item "My heart beats rapidly when I am in a dance or party" was rephrased as "My heart beats rapidly when I am in a social gathering" to broaden its applicability. Similarly, "Some people have labeled me as withdrawn" was modified to "Some people have labeled me as an introvert." The corrected version of the instrument was used to produce a new copy.

To assess the reliability of the SPS in the present context, a pilot study was conducted involving 42 purposively selected students from a school in Zing Local Government Area, outside the study's main sample, to avoid contamination. Internal consistency reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. While the original instrument reported an acceptable internal consistency of $\alpha = .79$, the revised version used in this study yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of $\alpha = .96$, indicating excellent reliability. The intervention component of the study spanned six sessions of social skills training, after which the SPS was re-administered as a post-test to evaluate changes in shyness levels following the treatment.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test was employed to test Hypotheses 1 and 2 at the 0.05 level of significance. This nonparametric statistical method is appropriate for analyzing paired data, such as pre- and post-intervention scores obtained from the same participants. It is particularly useful in cases where the assumptions of parametric tests, such as normal distribution of differences, may not be met. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test is designed to assess whether there is a statistically significant difference in the median scores of two related samples. It compares the direction and magnitude of changes between paired observations, such as those obtained before and after an intervention, by ranking the absolute differences, assigning signs (+ or -) based on the direction of change, and analyzing the sum of the signed ranks. This test was deemed appropriate for the present study, as it allowed the researchers to examine the effect of the social skills training intervention on participants' levels of shyness, using repeated measures data from a single sample. The dependent variable – shyness - was measured both before and after the intervention using the Shyness Personality Scale (SPS). The Wilcoxon signed-rank test enabled a robust analysis of whether the observed changes in shyness scores were statistically significant and attributable to the intervention.

Results Research Question One

To what extent is the effect of social skills training on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro LGA of Taraba State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviations scores on the effect of social skills on shyness

Shyness	N	mean			std. dev		percentiles
		25 th	50 th	75 th			
Pretest	20	3.79	0.65		3.26	3.81	4.34
Post-test	20	2.03	0.96		1.45	1.79	2.64

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Results in Table 1 show that before the administration of social skills, the pre-test mean score on shyness was 3.79, with a standard deviation of 0.65. The post-test mean score is 2.03, with a standard deviation of 0.96. The median scores indicated in percentiles that shyness reduced to 1.79 on the post-test from 3.81 on the post-test, an indication that social skills reduced students' shyness in secondary school.

Research Question Two

What is the difference in the mean shyness of high shyness male and female students exposed to social skills training in secondary schools in Yorro LGA of Taraba State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviations score on the shyness of male and female students exposed to social skills training in secondary schools in Taraba State

Gender	N		Pretest (shyness)		Posttest (shyness)		mean		Mean diff
	mean	std. dev	mean	std. dev	gain	female	male	std. dev	
	2.05	1.03	-1.80	0.24	3.61	0.82	15	3.85	0.61
			0.85	-1.63	1.98	0.07	5		

Shyness in both males and females shows a decrease from the pretest to the posttest. For females, the mean shyness score decreased from 3.85 to 2.05, while for males, it decreased from 3.61 to 1.98. This suggests a reduction in shyness levels for both female and male students after the treatment. The standard deviation for females increased from 0.61 to 1.03, indicating greater variability in posttest shyness scores compared to pretest scores. For males, the standard deviation slightly decreased from 0.82 to 0.85, indicating relatively consistent variability in scores before and after the treatment. Females had a mean reduction in shyness of -1.80, while males had a mean reduction of -1.63. These mean reductions indicate a significant decrease in shyness levels for both genders, with females showing a slightly larger reduction than males. The pretest mean difference between females and males was 0.24, indicating that females started with slightly higher shyness scores than males. The posttest mean difference was 0.07, suggesting that shyness scores for both genders were quite similar after the intervention, with females having slightly lower scores. The mean reduction difference of 0.17 indicates that females experienced a slightly larger decrease in shyness scores compared to males. Overall, the reduction in mean shyness scores from pretest to posttest for both genders suggests that the intervention was effective in decreasing shyness levels. The slightly larger reduction in shyness scores for females compared to males indicates that the intervention may have been marginally more effective for females.

Hypothesis three

Social skills training does not have a significant effect on secondary school students' shyness in Yorro LGA of Taraba State.

Table 3: Wilcoxon signed-rank test of the effect of social skills on the shyness of secondary school students in Yorro L.G.A. of Taraba State

	Post-test	Pre-test	
-N	40		
Z	-3.435	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.001

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Results from Table 3 show the Wilcoxon signed rank test conducted to compare the effect of social skills training on the shyness of secondary school students. The results indicate that the difference between pre-

test scores and post-test scores is statistically significant as indicated by $z = -3.338, p = 0.00 < 0.05$. The magnitude of the difference in the pretest and post-test scores

$\frac{z}{\sqrt{N}} = .54$ indicates a large effect size. The median score on shyness decreased from the pretest ($M = 3.81$) to the post-test ($M = 1.79$). This is to say that social skills have contributed 54% to reducing shyness. Since the difference between shyness before and after therapy is statistically significant, the hypothesis that social skills training does not have a significant effect on the students' shyness in secondary school in Yorro LGA of Taraba State is hereby rejected. That is social skills training has a significant effect on the shyness of secondary school students in Yorro LGA of Taraba State.

Hypothesis four

Social skills training does not have a significant effect on male and female secondary school students' shyness in Yorro LGA of Taraba State.

	Social Skills Training Shyness Female - Shyness Male
N	19
Z	-.405 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.686

- a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test
- b. Based on negative ranks.

Results from Table 4 show the Wilcoxon signed rank test conducted to compare the effect of social skills training on the shyness of male and female secondary school students in Yorro LGA of Taraba State. The results indicate that the difference between male scores and female scores is statistically insignificant as indicated by $z = -.405, p = 0.686 > 0.05$. Since the *p-value* is greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis which states that Social skills training does not have a significant effect on the shyness of male and female secondary school students in Yorro LGA of Taraba State is retained. That is social skills training has no significant effect on the shyness of male and female secondary school students in Yorro LGA of Taraba State. The male mean score on shyness ($M = 1.98$) is lower than the female mean score ($M = 2.20$). This is to say that social skills training is more effective for males than females. The magnitude of the difference in the z male and female scores $\frac{z}{\sqrt{N}} = -0.092$ indicates a small effect size.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that there is a 54% reduction in shyness due to social skills training on high-shyness students in Secondary Schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. There was a significant effect of social skills training on the high shyness of students in secondary schools in Yorro LGA of Taraba State, Nigeria. This implies that the use of social skills training had a significant effect on students' level of shyness. The finding also agrees with Vidyanand, Shriharsha, & Natekar (2022), that a social skills training programme on self-esteem and social anxiety among students was effective. The finding agrees with Ömer and Gökmen (2017), that the social skill training had a positive effect on the social skill level of participants. The findings of the current study are in line with that of Tetono, Kuntoro and Savitri (2017) whose results indicated a rise in social skills of the target behaviour. The finding agrees with Ima-Osagie and Nwankwo (2019) that the

modelling technique was effective in decreasing the shyness of students in junior secondary school. This study is also in agreement with Abubakar (2021) whose study showed the efficacy of social skills training on social phobia of students in secondary school.

The finding agrees with Saeedi, Rezvani and Rezvan (2020) that self-expression training decreased shyness and behavioural incompatibility in the samples that were investigated. The present study is in line with Oguzie, Obi, and Nnadi, (2019) whose results showed that the selfmanagement technique was more effective in decreasing the shyness of the female participants than that of their male counterparts and that the gender difference in the efficacy of selfmanagement technique in decreasing the participants' shyness was not significant. The results of this study revealed that social skills training was more effective on males than females, though the effect was insignificant. Therefore, this study disagrees with Isyaku (2015) whose findings revealed the significant effects of the modelling and token reinforcement in reducing the shy behaviour between male and female secondary school students, and that females benefitted more from the treatments when compared to male participants.

The utilized social skills training as a therapeutic approach in the present study helped students who had difficulties relating to other people. The social skills training includes instructional methods and interventions that assist students with high shyness to improve and understand social behaviour. The aim of social skills training as used in the present study was to assist students in understanding the spoken and non-spoken actions that make up every day social encounters. This may be responsible for the significant effect of social skills training on students with high shyness in secondary schools in Yorro LGA of Taraba State, Nigeria.

Conclusions

Based on the outcome of the study, it was agreed that counselling interventions using social skills training reduce the level of shyness and increase the awareness of the consequences of shy behaviour of students in secondary school in Yorro LGA of Taraba State. From the report of the study, the researchers concluded that conscious efforts must be made by the Federal and State government, school management, teachers and guidance counsellors to focus on using these therapies and provide good counselling on secondary school students' behavioural problems such as shyness.

Recommendations

1. Principals in federal schools, State schools and Proprietors of private schools are encouraged to provide adequate counselling services phenomenon in schools and to employ the services of professional counsellors who will use Social Skills Training for effective treatment of students' behavioural problems such as shyness.
2. Educational experts in counselling should be encouraged to use social skills training for effective treatment of shyness among secondary school students.
3. Secondary school students should be encouraged to go to school counsellors for training on the use of social skills' training especially to curb behavioural problems such as shyness.
4. School management should from time to time organize seminars and workshops for all parents for sensitization on the use of social skills training to improve the shy behaviour of their wards. By this, parents will see the need to encourage their wards at home to practice the acquired counselling skills.

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. Efficacy of social skills training on the shyness of pupils in both public and private primary schools.

2. The replication of this same study in a different study area.
3. Efficacy of social skills training on other selected behavioural problems of students in secondary schools.

Reference

- Abubakar, H. (2021). Effect of cognitive restructuring and social skills training on social phobia among secondary school students in Kaduna Metropolis, Nigeria. Unpublished thesis submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria for the award of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Psychology.
- Ali, S. I., Abdel-Fatah, S. R., Mahmoud, A. S. & El-Sayad, S. M. (2018). Effect of social skills training program on self-esteem and aggression among children in residential institutions in Port Said City. *Archives of Nursing Practice and Care*, 4(1), 007-013.
- Côté, S. M., Larose, M. P., Geoffroy, M. C., Laurin, J., Vitaro, F., Tremblay, R. E. & Morin, I. O. (2017). Testing the impact of a social skill training versus waiting list control group for the reduction of disruptive behaviours and stress among preschool children in child care: The study protocol for a cluster randomized trial. *BMC Psychology*, 5(1):29.
- Datta, D., Datta, P. P., & Majumdar, K. K. (2015). Role of social interaction on quality of life. *National Journal of Medical Research*, 5(4), 290-292.
- D’Arcy, L. (2016). Shyness and shy people. Retrieved from <http://www.kidshealth.org/en/tees/shyness.html>.
- Guadalupe, F. (2016). Social skills training for autistic children: A comparison study between inclusion and mainstreaming education. California Lutheran University. Research Article 1: 16-18. Link: <https://goo.gl/JMn Cm6>
- Hall, A. J., & Merolla, A. J. (2020). Connecting everyday talk and time alone to global well-being. *Human Communication Research*, 46(1), 86-111.
- Ibaishwa, R.L. (2014). Shyness and emotional intelligence as predictors of mathematics anxiety among secondary school students in Makurdi, Benue State. *Journal of Educational Policy and Entrepreneurial Research*, 1(2), 11-21.
- Ima-Osagie, P. E. & Nwankwo, C. A. (2019). Effects of modelling technique on shyness among junior secondary school students in Benin Metropolis of Edo State. *British Journal of Education, Learning and Development Psychology*, 2(3), 6-20.
- Ima-osagie, Patricia Eghe & Obinell, S. U. (2020). Effects of shaping technique on shyness among junior secondary school students. *Global Scientific Journal*, 8(2).

- Isyaku, Y. (2015). Effects of modelling and token reinforcement technique on shy behaviour among secondary school students in Kano State, Nigeria. A thesis submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria for fulfilment of the Award of a Doctorate Degree.
- McAdams, B.T. (2014). Loneliness: A review of current literature, with implications for counselling and research. *Journal of Counselling and Development*, 6(8), 417-422.
- Nihayati, H. E., Tristiana, R. D., Junata, A. S. P., & Yusuf, A. (2017). Effect of Social Skills Training: Social Interaction Capabilities towards Social Isolation Clients. *Advances in Health Sciences Research*, 3, 121-125
- Oguzie, A. E., Ezunu, E. N., Uba, J. E. & Osagie, G. E. (2018). Effect of assertiveness training technique on shyness among secondary school students in Imo state. *Journal of the Nigerian Academy of Education*, 14(1), 84-97.
- Oguzie, A. E. (2016). Effect of assertiveness training technique on shyness among secondary school students in Imo state. A thesis submitted to the school of postgraduate studies, Nnamdi, Azikiwe University Awka Anambra state for fulfilment of the Award of a Masters Degree.
- Oguzie, A. E., Joy S., Obi, C. & Nnadi, G. (2019). Effect of self-management technique on shyness among secondary school students in Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 7(5).
- Okore, C., Asatsa, S., & Ntarangwe, M. (2021). Effect of social skills training on the self-concept of teenage mothers, A case study of training college in Kenya. *Journal of Social Sciences and Economic Review*, 3(2), 1-09.
- Ömer, G. & Gökmen, D. (2017). Effects of Social Skill Training Program on Social Skills of Young People. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 13(11):7365-7373
- Rahmani, R. & Baniyadi, H. (2013). The effectiveness of nonverbal communication training on reducing shyness. *The Journal of Thought & Behaviour in Clinical Psychology (JTBCP)*, 7(26), 47-65.
- Saeedi, A. S., Rezvani, A. F. & Rezvan, A. (2020). Assertiveness training on shyness and behavioural incompatibility in female students. *Middle Eastern Journal of Disability Studies (MEJDS)*, 10:88. URL: <http://jdisabilstud.org/article-1-1743-en.html>
- Tetono, M. M. D.; Kuntoro, I. A. & Savitri, L. S. Y. (2017). The Implementation of Social Skills Training (SST) to Improve the Social Skills of an Adolescent with Peer Relationship Problems at School. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR)*, 13(5)

Uba, M. B. & Idieune, O. B. (2016). Effects of assertiveness training technique on enhancing shyness among primary school pupils in Onitsha Urban of Anambra State. *Journal of the Educational Psychologists*, 10(1), 210-216.

Vidyanand, K. S., Shriharsha, C., Natekar, D. S. (2022). Effectiveness of social skill training programme on social anxiety and self-esteem among adolescents. *International Journal of Science & Healthcare Research*, 7(1): 35-40.